

THE ANALYSIS AND MEASUREMENT OF RESIDUAL STRESS IN CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES INTERFACE

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ABSTRACT

Due to misfit of the elastic coefficients of fiber and matrix, the interface of ceramic matrix composites is subjected to residual stresses which can be on the order of giga-pascal. Therefore, the residual stress of the interface has great effect on the mechanical properties of composites. In this paper, the micromechanical model is a composite cylinder with a fiber embedded in concentric cylinder of matrix materials. Considering this model as a 3D axisymmetrical problem, the expressions of interfacial residual stresses σ_t , σ_r , τ_{rz} are presented. These results agree well with experimental results by Laser Raman Spectroscopy Technique.

INTRODUCTION

Due to misfit of the elastic coefficients of fiber and matrix, the interface of ceramic matrix composites (CMC) is subjected to residual stresses which can be on the order of giga-pascal. The residual stresses can cause the interface debonds and allow the main crack to propagate beyond the fiber which remains intact. The intact fiber then bridges the crack faces, exerting a closing traction which shields the crack tip from the stress applied to the materials as shown in Fig. 1. Therefore, the residual stress of the interface has great effect on the mechanical properties of materials. Hence, how to predict the residual stress is an important problem.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of crack propagation through CMC

MECHANICS OF MATERIALS APPROACH

Using Mechanics of Materials Approach, which is assumed that the strains in the fiber direction

of a unidirectional fibrous composite are the same in the fiber as in the matrix, as shown in Fig. 2, the residual thermal stresses in the fiber and matrix are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_f &= E_f E_m V_m \frac{\alpha_m - \alpha_f}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} \Delta T \\ \sigma_m &= E_f E_m V_f \frac{\alpha_f - \alpha_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} \Delta T \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Micromechanical Model of Mechanics of Materials Approach

where E_f , E_m are Young's modulus of fiber and matrix; V_f , V_m are volume fractions of fiber and matrix, and ΔT (usually $\Delta T < 0$) is temperature gradient, and α_f , α_m are coefficients of thermal expansion of fiber and matrix respectively.

The key feature of the Mechanics of Materials Approach is that certain simplifying assumptions as mentioned above, are made. The Poisson's ratios of fiber and matrix are ignored.

ANALYSIS OF RESIDUAL STRESS BY THEORY OF ELASTICITY

In this paper, a new, reasonable expression to predict the residual thermal stress of composite interface by use of Theory of Elasticity.

GENERALIZED PLANE STRAIN PROBLEM

The micromechanical model is a composite cylinder with a fiber embedded in a concentric cylinder of matrix materials as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Micromechanical Model of generalized plane strain problem

The outer cylinder is made of matrix and the inner one is made of fiber. The cylinders are supposed to be engaged by shrink fit. The difference in diameter, corresponding to a radial pressure p at the interface, is given by

$$\delta = ap \left[\frac{1 - \nu_f}{E_f} + \frac{(1 + \nu_m) + (1 - \nu_m)V_f}{E_m(1 - \nu_f)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where p is the normal stress at the interface, and a is the radius of fiber.

Considering Poisson's ratio effect, the difference in diameter of two cylinders, corresponding to the radical thermal deformation, is given by

$$\delta = a \Delta \alpha \Delta T + a(\nu_f \epsilon_f - \nu_m \epsilon_m) \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_f - \alpha_m$

By equating Eqn (2) and (3), we have

$$p = \frac{B}{A}(\alpha_f - \alpha_m) \tag{4}$$

where

$$A = \frac{1 - \gamma_f}{E_f} + \frac{(1 + \gamma_m) + (1 - \gamma_m)V_f}{E_m(1 - V_f)} \tag{5}$$

$$B = 1 + \frac{\gamma_f V_m E_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} + \frac{\gamma_m V_f E_f}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} \tag{6}$$

By Theory of Elasticity, for fiber (inner cylinder),

$$\sigma_r = \sigma_\theta = p \tag{7}$$

for matrix (outer cylinder),

$$\sigma_r = \frac{p}{1 - V_f} \frac{a^2}{r^2} - \frac{V_f}{1 - V_f} p$$

$$\sigma_\theta = -\frac{p}{1 - V_f} \frac{a^2}{r^2} - \frac{V_f}{1 - V_f} p \tag{8}$$

Therefore the axial stresses in fiber and matrix induced by these stresses expressed in Eqn(8) will be

$$\sigma_f'' = 2\gamma_f p$$

$$\sigma_m'' = -2\gamma_m \frac{V_f}{1 - V_f} p \tag{9}$$

Hence the residual stresses in fiber and matrix are

$$\sigma_f = \left[\frac{E_f E_m V_m}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} + 2\gamma_f \frac{B}{A} \right] (\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \Delta T$$

$$\sigma_m = \left[\frac{E_f E_m V_f}{E_f V_f + E_m V_m} + 2\gamma_m \frac{B}{A} \right] (\alpha_f - \alpha_m) \Delta T \tag{10}$$

Obviously, the first term of right side of Eqn (10) is the residual stress of the solution by Mechanics of Materials Approach. The second term is approximately 40% of the first term in Eqn (10). Hence the prediction of the interfacial residual stress by Mechanics of Materials Approach is too low.

3D AXISYMMETRIC PROBLEM

Consider the model of the composite cylinder as 3D axisymmetric problem as shown in Fig. 4. This model is also a composite cylinder with a fiber embedded in a concentric cylinder of matrix material.

Figure 4. Micromechanical Model of 3D Axisymmetric Problem

Assume the displacement of fiber in Z direction be

$$u_z^f = u_0 + \frac{r^2}{a^2}(u_a - u_0), \quad 0 \leq r \leq a \tag{11}$$

Where u_a, u_0 are displacements of the fiber in Z direction at $r = a$ and $r = 0$ respectively. Obviously, this displacement expressed in Eqn (11) can satisfy the following boundary conditions:

when $r=a$, $\tau_r=\tau_m$ and
 when $r=b$, $r=0$, $\tau=0$

Assume the displacement of matrix in Z direction be

$$u_z^m = u_b + \frac{b^2 \ln \frac{r}{b} - \frac{1}{2}(r^2 - b^2)}{b^2 \ln \frac{a}{b} - \frac{1}{2}(a^2 - b^2)}(u_a - u_b) \quad (12)$$

where u_b is the displacement of matrix in Z direction at $r=b$.

For simplifying the calculation, the displacement and strain of fiber are substituted by its average displacement u_f and strain ϵ_f respectively, then

$$u_f = \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \int_0^a \int_0^{2\pi} [u_o + \frac{r^2}{a^2}(u_a - u_o)] r dr d\theta = \frac{1}{2}(u_a + u_o)$$

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{du_f}{dz} = \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_a + \epsilon_o) \quad (13)$$

Then, by equations of equilibrium and boundary conditions (including at interface), the residual stress in fiber is

$$\sigma_f = (\sigma_k + \frac{a_i}{a_j})e^{-qz} - \frac{a_i}{a_j}$$

$$q = \sqrt{a_j} \quad (14)$$

The residual shear stress τ_{rz} and radial stress σ_r along the interface are :

$$\tau_{rz} = \frac{aq}{2}(\sigma_k + \frac{a_i}{a_j})e^{-qz} \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_r = \frac{E_f}{1 + \gamma_f} (\frac{A_f}{(1 - 2\gamma_f)} - \frac{B_f}{a^2}) - \frac{E_f}{1 - 2\gamma_f} (\alpha_f \Delta T - \frac{V_f + \epsilon_o}{1 + V_f}) \quad (16)$$

where σ_k is the uniformly distributed external load on fiber and matrix. Then, from equilibrium condition in Z direction, we have

$$\pi \sigma_r a^2 + 2\pi \int_0^b \sigma_r^m r dr = \sigma_k b^2 \pi \quad (17)$$

where a and b are radius of fiber and matrix, as shown in Fig. 3.

In Eqn(14) and (15), a_1 and a_i are determined by

$$a_i = C_j [-\frac{1 - 2\gamma_m}{\gamma_m} (\frac{a^2}{2b^2}) \frac{d_1 b_2 - d_2 b_1}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1} + \frac{1 - 2\gamma_m}{\gamma_m} (\frac{1}{2(1 - 2\gamma_m)} + \frac{a^2}{2b^2})$$

$$\cdot \frac{a_1 d_2 - a_2 d_1}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1} - \frac{1 + \gamma_m}{\gamma_m} \gamma_m \Delta T] - a_j \cdot \varphi'_f$$

$$a_j = \frac{C_j}{A'_f} [1 - \frac{1 - 2\gamma_m}{\gamma_m} \frac{a^2}{2b^2} \frac{b_2 c_1 - b_1 c_2}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1} + \frac{1 - 2\gamma_m}{\gamma_m} (\frac{1}{2(1 - 2\gamma_m)} + \frac{a^2}{2b^2})$$

$$\cdot \frac{a_1 c_2 - a_2 c_1}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1}] \quad (18)$$

where

$$\varphi'_f = \frac{E_f \gamma_f}{(1 + \gamma_f)(1 - 2\gamma_f)} \cdot \frac{d_1 d_2 - d_2 d_1}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1} - \frac{\alpha_f E_f \Delta T}{1 - 2\gamma_f}$$

$$A'_f = A_f + \frac{E_f \gamma_f}{(1 + \gamma_f)(1 - 2\gamma_f)} \cdot \frac{b_2 c_1 - b_1 c_2}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1}$$

$$C_j = 4G_m \cdot cc \cdot dd \quad (19)$$

here

$$cc = \frac{a^2 - b^2}{2b^2 \ln \frac{a}{b} - (a^2 - b^2)} \cdot \frac{1}{a^2}$$

$$dd = \frac{4b^2 \ln \frac{a}{b} - 2(a^2 - b^2)}{4b^2 \ln \frac{a}{b} - (2 - \frac{G_m}{G_f})(a^2 - b^2)}$$

$$A_f = E_f + \frac{2E_f \gamma_f^2}{(1 - 2\gamma_f)(1 + \gamma_f)}$$

$$A'_f = \frac{E_f \gamma_f}{(1 + \gamma_f)(1 - 2\gamma_f)} \cdot \frac{b_2 c_1 - b_1 c_2}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1} + A_f \quad (20)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_1 &= a^2 \frac{E_f \gamma_f}{(1 + \gamma_f)(1 - 2\gamma_m)} - b_0 \frac{1 - 2\gamma_f}{\gamma_m} \frac{a^2}{2b^2} \\
 a_2 &= \frac{E_f}{2(1 + \gamma_f)(1 - 2\gamma_f)} + \frac{E_m}{2(1 + \gamma_m)} - (1 - dd) \cdot aa \cdot \frac{1 - 2\gamma_m}{\gamma_m} \frac{a^2}{2b^2} \\
 b_2 &= \frac{-(1 - \gamma_m)E_m}{(1 + \gamma_m)(1 - 2\gamma_m)} + (1 - dd) \cdot aa \cdot \frac{1 - 2\gamma_m}{\gamma_m} \left(\frac{1}{2(1 - 2\gamma_m)} + \frac{a^2}{2b^2} \right) \\
 b_1 &= \frac{E_m(b^2 - a^2)}{(1 + \gamma_m)(1 - 2\gamma_m)} - b_0 \frac{1 - 2\gamma_m}{\gamma_m} \left(\frac{1}{2(1 - 2\gamma_m)} + \frac{a^2}{2b^2} \right) \\
 c_1 &= -a^2 A_f - A_m \cdot bb \cdot dd \\
 c_2 &= aa \cdot dd \\
 d_1 &= \sigma_a \cdot b^2 + a^2 \frac{\alpha_f E_f \Delta T}{1 - 2\gamma_f} + \frac{\alpha_m E_m \Delta T}{1 - 2\gamma_m} (b^2 - a^2) - b_0 \frac{1 + \gamma_m}{\gamma_m} \alpha_m \Delta T \\
 d_2 &= \frac{1 + \gamma_m}{\gamma_m} \alpha_m \Delta T \cdot (1 - dd) \cdot aa - \frac{E_m \alpha_m \Delta T}{1 - 2\gamma_m} + \frac{E_f \alpha_f \Delta T}{1 - 2\gamma_f} \tag{21}
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_0 &= \frac{A_m(b^2 - a^2) - A_m \cdot bb \cdot dd}{E_m \gamma_m} - \frac{E_f \gamma_f}{(1 + \gamma_f)(1 - 2\gamma_f)} \\
 aa &= \frac{E_m \gamma_m}{(1 + \gamma_m)(1 - 2\gamma_m)} - \frac{E_f \gamma_f}{(1 + \gamma_f)(1 - 2\gamma_f)} \\
 &\quad - 4a^2 b^2 \ln \frac{a}{b} - (a^4 - b^4) \\
 bb &= \frac{4a^2 b^2 \ln \frac{a}{b} - (a^4 - b^4)}{-4b^2 \ln \frac{a}{b} - 2(a^2 - b^2)} \\
 A_m &= E_m + \frac{2E_m \gamma_m^2}{(1 - 2\gamma_m)(1 + \gamma_m)} \\
 A_f &= \frac{(b_2 c_1 - b_1 c_2) \epsilon_f + (d_1 b_2 - d_2 b_1)}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1} \tag{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\epsilon_a = dd \cdot \epsilon_f + (1 - dd) \epsilon_b \tag{23}$$

here,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \epsilon_b &= -\frac{(1 - 2\gamma_m)}{\gamma_m} \left(\frac{A_m}{2(1 - 2\gamma_m)} - \frac{a^2}{2b^2} A_f + \frac{a^2}{2b^2} A_m \right) + \frac{(1 + \gamma_m)}{\gamma_m} \alpha_m \Delta T \\
 A_m &= \frac{(a_1 c_2 - a_2 c_1) \epsilon_f + (a_1 d_2 - a_2 d_1)}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1}
 \end{aligned}$$

ϵ_f is the average strain as shown in Eqn(13),

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_m &= \frac{a^2}{2} (A_f - A_m) \\
 B_f &= 0 \text{ (when } r \rightarrow 0, \sigma_r \neq \infty \therefore B_f = 0) \tag{24}
 \end{aligned}$$

MEASUREMENT OF RESIDUAL STRESS BY LASER RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

PRINCIPLE OF THE RAMAN TECHNIQUE

A new technique for the determination of fiber strain in composites has been developed over the years. The strain sensitive property of high performance fibers is a vibration frequency which can be measured by Laser Raman Spectroscopy (LRS).

A typical spectrum from a free-standing carbon fiber in air is presented in Fig. 5. The relationship of Raman frequency versus tensile strain is normally by stressing a single fiber in air while Raman spectra are taken along the fiber length at each level of applied load. The difference between the Raman frequency values obtained at each level of strain and that of the free-standing fiber represents the Raman frequency shift. In Fig. 6 the Raman frequency shift R is plotted as a function of applied strain ϵ^* for the 1593cm^{-1} band of the carbon fibre spectrum, and a linear relationship is obtained. The negative slope of the least-squares fitted straight line represents the sensitivity of the strain sensor and has been termed the Raman frequency gauge factor. The linear relationship between Raman frequency and tensile strain holds for a whole range of carbon and aramid fibers.

Figure 5. Raman spectrum of a carbon fiber in both first and second order frequency regions

Figure 6. Raman frequency as a function of tensile strain for the 1593cm⁻¹ band of carbon fibre.

CALIBRATION OF FIBER

In order to solve the problem of stressing a single fiber the method of stress frozen in the photoelastic materials will be employed.

The dog-bone specimen adopted is shown in Fig. 7. The matrix of the specimen is epoxy 711[#], and curing solvent is DDM. They are 100 : 17 by weight. The specimens are hung into the electric oven and subjected by the loads of 0, 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300g. The temperature in the oven is gradually increased until 110~120°C reached. Then these specimens are kept in this temperature for 1.5~2.0 hours. The speed of temperature decreased is 3°C per hour until the room temperature is reached.

The cross-sectional area of the specimen is $s=5 \times 5=25\text{mm}^2$, Young's modulus of the specimen is $E=0.25 \times 10^9\text{N/m}^2$, and the strain of the fibre in the specimen is $\epsilon^* = P/sE$, where P is the tensile load.

Fig 7. Dog-bone specimen

The Raman spectra are taken along the fibre length at each level of applied load (0, 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300g) The typical Raman frequency at strain $\epsilon^* = 0.373\%$ ($P=200g$) is shown in Fig. 8. Raman frequency shift has been plotted as a function of applied strain for the 1593cm^{-1} and (see Fig. 5) as shown in Fig. 6. The equation of the least-squares fitted straight line is

$$R = 1595 - 40.2\epsilon^* \tag{25}$$

The peak of the Raman frequency shift is $R = 1593\text{cm}^{-1}$ as shown in Fig. 5. Therefore the residual axial strain of carbon fibre at the interface of C/SiC is $\epsilon^* = 0.05\%$.

Figure 8. Typical Raman spectrum for carbon fibre ($\epsilon^* = 0.373\%$, $P=200g$)

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Consider C/SiC ceramic composites. The properties are $E_r = 230\text{GPa}$, $\gamma_r = 0.25$, $\alpha_r = 5.3 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$; $E_m = 440\text{GPa}$, $\gamma_m = 0.25$, $\alpha_m = 4.7 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$; $\Delta T = 20^\circ\text{C} - 1200^\circ\text{C} = -1180^\circ\text{C}$. By use of Eqn (14) ~ (16), the distributions of residual stresses $\sigma_z^i, \sigma_r^i, \tau_{rz}^i$ along the interface of C/SiC are shown in fig. 9.

Figure 9. Variations of $\sigma_z^i, \sigma_r^i, \tau_{rz}^i$ along the interface of C/SiC

For comparison of such predicted residual stresses (analytical solutions) with experimental results, Laser Raman Spectroscopy Technique is used. All these results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of predicated residual stresses at the interface of C/SiC with experimental results

Approach	Axial strain of Fiber $\epsilon_z(\%)$	Axial stress of Fiber $\sigma_t(\text{MPa})$
Mechanics of Materials	0.055	126.5
General Plane Strain Problem	0.055	175.0
3D Axisymmetrical Problem	0.055	183.3
Experimental Results	0.050	—

CONCLUSIONS

1. The axial stresses predicted by two approaches of Theory of Elasticity agree pretty well, where the discrepancy is only 4.53%. If these results are compared with those of Mechanics of Materials, the discrepancy will be as high as 31.0%. This is mainly due to transverse strains mismatch at the interface.
2. The variations of shear stress τ_{rz} along the interface could be only formulated by 3D axisymmetrical problem as shown in Fig. 9. Apparently, the gradients of $\sigma'_t, \sigma'_z, \tau'_{rz}$ are steep near the free end of the fiber. When $z/a < 2$, these gradients will be zero.
3. When $\alpha_t > \alpha_m, \sigma'_t$ is in tension. The existence of σ'_t, τ'_{rz} at the interface will produce mixed mode of fracture with mode I and mode II. When $\alpha_t < \alpha_m, \sigma'_t$ is in compression, hence there will be friction force along the interface. In addition, τ'_{rz} will produce fracture mode of pure shear mode II. Under both conditions, when τ'_{rz} reaches the interfacial shear strength, the interfacial debonding will occur.
4. The interfacial debonding length will be affected by the rate of energy released. Under the former condition, the residual stress will improve the fracture toughness of CMC. But when the residual stresses, especially σ_z , are too big, the fibre will be broken, or the debonding along the interface will come into existence in large scale. Thus, the residual stress will decrease the fracture toughness of CMC.
5. Considering the model as a 3D axisymmetrical problem, the expressions (14) ~ (16) to predict the residual stresses of CMC interface more reasonable. Therefore, these expressions are highly recommended to predict the interfacial residual stresses of CMC.

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